

FLEXURAL QUALITIES OF NEW NANOCOMPOSITES FOR RESTORATION BASED ON DIGITAL IMAGE PROCESSING AND POLYMERIZATION BY LIGHT TREATMENT**¹Dr. Shyamsing Thakur**

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to present some of the most significant image processing technologies that are utilised in dental restoration, as well as to emphasise the relevance of image processing technology in dental restoration and its applicability. The following are examples of information sources: Using the search phrases "tooth colour," relevant English papers that were published between the years 1990 and 2021 were located using a computer-based internet search of HighWire biomedical full-text electronic resources on the internet. During this time, we searched for related Chinese publications using the keywords "computer aided design, tooth, digital" and "image processing,

tooth" in the VIP database from 2001 to 2007 and the Wanfang database from 2000 to 2021, respectively. Both of these databases covered the years 2001 to 2007. Choices Made Regarding Research: Over two hundred and fifty articles were compiled, and from those, the top ten were selected. The first kind of research included written materials on tooth bleaching as well as the components and production process of baked porcelain teeth. The second type of research included basic investigations, case reports, or repeated studies. Only articles that discussed the following topics were read in their entirety: 1 the current state of tooth damage in China and the importance of dental restoration; 2 the acquisition of digital tooth images and preconditioning of tooth images; 3 the three-dimensional image reconstruction of general tooth films; 4 computer-aided colour matching technology; and 5 current tooth restoration products both in China and abroad. Extraction of Data In order to conduct this research, a total of twenty-six different pieces of literature on a variety of subjects, such as digital dental image capture and preconditioning, three-dimensional image reconstruction of general dental films, and computer assisted colour matching technology, were selected as samples. The Process of Information Synthesis: Digitized X-ray imaging technology is the current development trend in the field of dental diagnostics. In picture preconditioning, the most common ways are geometrical alteration and image enhancement. In dental restoration, additional essential approaches include three-dimensional image reconstruction and computer-assisted colour matching.

According to the findings, the composites with particular monomers (Digital image processing, methacrylamide, methacrylic acid, and 1-6 hexanediol methacrylate) for group (D) that were reinforced with silica nanoparticle have elevated flexural properties as compared with other types of the prepared nanocomposite, where these values reached to (144 MPa and 5.4 GPa) for flexural strength and flexural modulus respectively.

Keywords: Flexural strength, Digital image processing, flexural modulus, light-cured nanocomposites, dental composites.

Introduction

Due to the growing demand from dental patients for tooth-colored restorations over the last 45 years, the field of employed dental restorative composite materials has steadily evolved.

Due to their superior mechanical, biocompatibility, and cosmetic qualities as well as their high coherence potential with tooth structure, acceptable handling, and affordable cost, among other attributes, resin-based composites are widely used in the medical area, particularly in dentistry [1].

The four main components of resin-based composites utilised in dental applications are the polymer matrix, filler particles, coupling agent, and initiator-accelerator system [2].

While filler particles are an inorganic component that may be employed to improve the mechanical and physical characteristics of the resin matrix, the matrix is composed mostly of organic monomers that are typically polymerized by visible light activation [3].

Despite the significant advancement of resin-based composites, restorative composites now show additional limitations that really affect their durability and service life because of their subpar mechanical strength and excessive polymerization shrinkage [4].

Mechanical characteristics of resin-based composites are primarily influenced by their composition,

microstructure, and filler particle dispersion [5].

A significant relationship between the mechanical qualities of composites and the use of various kinds of monomers as resin basis and the selection of the more suitable fillers in these composite to achieve to more adequate mechanical properties has been documented by a large number of authors.

Silica was added to natural hydroxyapatite (NHAp) and mixed with an organic matrix resin in order to study the effects of different weight fractions (0, 5, 15, and 20 wt%) of NHAp and silica as inorganic fillers in dental resin (50% bisphenol A glycidyl methacrylate (BisGMA)/ 25% triethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEGDMA)/ 25% hydroxyethyl methacrylate (The findings indicate that the weight fraction of HAp and silica in the composite affects the mechanical characteristics, and the optimal composition (85 wt% of HAp and 15 wt% of silicate) achieved the greatest values of flexural and compressive strength [6].

In 2018, M. S. AlAjely et al. created a brand-new dental composite using Bis GMA/TEGDMA in a 70/30 composition ratio as matrix resins and various calcium fluoroaluminosilicate glass filler ratios. The three-point bending test used to determine the static flexural strength and modulus in accordance with ISO-4049 standards. Flexural modulus of 11.29 GPa and the greatest flexural strength of 90.35 MPa were also attained as a consequence [7].

Dental resin composites were created in 2019 by Sukriti Yadav and Swati Gangwar using photo-curable technology and different amounts of functionalized nHAPs (0, 4, 8 and 12%wt.). The matrixes of this composite consisted of 2-hydroxyethyl-methacrylate (HEMA) and tri-ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEGDMA), which were utilised as diluent monomers, and bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate (Image processing) as a base monomer. The findings reveal that although the flexural strength of the composite decreased with increases in filler quantity, hardness and compressive strength increased, even if this value is still more than the acceptable limit of flexural strength in dental applications (i.e. 74.2MPa)[8].

Another group studied the impact of filler size on the aggregation of these fillers, and then their impact on the mechanical properties of dental resin composites that were calculated at different filler loadings (20 wt% up to 76.5 wt%) of silica particles (SiNP) with 80 nm nano size, and amorphous barium-alumina borosilicate (BaAlBoSi) microparticles (1.0 μ m), added to resin matrix made The research came to the conclusion that the flexural strengths were best at the maximum filler concentration of Si nanoparticles (20wt%) and lowest at (BaAlBoSi) fillers. The decrease in flexural strength of (BaAlBoSi) composites is related to the larger filler particles, which resulted in good particle size distribution [9].

The objective of the study under consideration is to create novel dental composite materials by combining a variety of new monomers with Image Processing (such as methacrylamide, 2-ethylhexylmethacrylate, methacrylic acid, and methacrylate), which were then individually strengthened with four different types of inorganic nanoparticles (ZrO₂, SiO₂, HA, and Al₂O₃). The flexural properties of these composites were evaluated, along with the impact of the chemical composition of the composites' components on those properties, in order to characterise them. The results of all prepared composites were compared in order to determine which composites were best for use in dental applications.

Materials and Methods

In this research six types of matrices were prepared, are listed in Table 1 in six groups (A, B, C, D, E and F) each matrix was prepared from different monomers, where 2,2 propyl bisphenol glycidyl dimethacrylate (Image proessing) is the base material in all matrices, with other different monomers each has its own function. As well as, four types of inorganic nanoparticles (ZrO₂, SiO₂, HA and Al₂O₃) were used as nano-fillers for various purposes, each type of nanoparticles has different particle sizes are ((30-40), (10-20), 25 and (20-40) nm) respectively. All chemical materials were supplied by Sigma Aldrich/USA and MERCK/Germany companies.

Table (1): Chemical Composition of the Matrices Resins of Prepared Composites.

Groups	Monomers	Adding Ratio	Monomers Mixing Time
A	1. IMAGE PROESSING 2. 2-ethylhexylmethacrylate 3. methylmethacrylate 4. 1-6 hexanediol methacrylate	40% 20% 20% 20%	50min
B	1. IMAGE PROESSING 2. methacrylic acid 3. methacrylate 4.1-6hexanediol methacrylate	40% 20% 20% 20%	50min
C	1. IMAGE PROESSING 2. methacrylic acid 3. polyethylene glycol 3500 4.1-6hexanediol methacrylate	40% 20% 20% 20%	70min
D	1. IMAGE PROESSING 2. methacrylamide 3. methacrylic acid 4. 1-6 hexanediol methacrylate	40% 20% 20% 20%	90min
E	1. IMAGE PROESSING 2. 2-ethylhexylmethacrylate 3. polyethylglycol 4. .bisphenoladimethacrylate 5. 1-6 hexanediol methacrylate	40% 20% 10% 10% 20%	70min
F	1. IMAGE PROESSING 2. methacryate 3. polyethylene glycol	40% 20% 20%	70min

	4.	1-6hexanediol methacrylate	20%	
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Nanocomposite Preparation

Each group shown in Table 1 was combined for around 90 minutes with N2 gas present to remove dissolved oxygen, followed by the addition of 0.4gm of zinc oxide as an antibacterial agent. To determine the optimal addition percentage, one kind of nano-filler (HA) was first added to two sets of matrix monomers (D and H) at various weight fractions (1, 2, 3, and 4%wt). Each group of the matrix monomers listed previously in Table 1 had separate nano-fillers (ZrO2, SiO2, HA, and Al2O3) supplied at a consistent weight-fraction ratio (2%wt). Additionally, 0.5 weight percent of DMAEMA as an accelerator and 0.5 weight percent of camphor quinone as an initiator were added to the mixture and continuously mixed for 20 minutes, which is regarded as the last mixing step before manufacturing composite materials.

Then, using an EliparFreelight2LED, 3 M ESPE light curing unit with an intensity of 1500 mW/cm2, all of the specimens were exposed to light to cure them. For 60 seconds, the samples were irradiated in various locations. The specimens were kept in distilled water at 37°C and 100% humidity for 48 hours after polymerization and before the flexural strength (FS) test.

The Flexural Test:

The flexural strength test was performed according to ISO 4049:2019 by the three-point bending test[10]. Five specimens of each composite type were prepared with dimensioned (2mm ×2mm× 25mm) as shown in Figure (1).

The samples were fitted between two supports with a 20 mm span between them the speed of the test was 0.75 mm/min until fracture was occurred. The flexural strength(MPa)was determined using the Equation (1);[11]

$$\text{Flexural strength (MPa) for three - point bend test} = \sigma_{\text{bend}} = \frac{3 FL}{2wh^2} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where F is the max of applied load (N), L is the span between the supports (20 mm), w is the width (2 mm), and h is the thickness (2 mm).

The flexural modulus (E_f), is calculated in the elastic region was determined from Equation 2:

$$\text{Flexural modulus} = E_f = \frac{FL^3}{4\delta w^3} = \frac{mL^3}{4wh^3} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where δ is the deflection of the beam when a force F is applied, m is the slope of the load (F) /deflection curve.

Figure (1): Flexural test where (a) test specimens and (b) schematic illustration of the flexural strength test.

Results and Discussion of Flexural Test :

The kind of polymeric materials, filler type, filler ratio, distribution of fillers, and bonding of the fillers within the composite material all affect the flexural characteristics of polymeric composites. The produced matrices were put through a flexural test in order to determine which material would be the best to utilize as a matrix for dental composites. Figures 2 and 3 show the results of flexural strength and flexural modulus, respectively, as a function of matrix type (A, B, C, D, E and F). According to these Figures, different values for the flexural strength and flexural modulus were found based on the copolymer components created as the matrix for dental composites. Additionally, it was observed that the samples with the matrix made of group D monomers had the greatest values of the bending characteristics, measuring 121 MPa and 4.38GPa, respectively. While the two samples made from monomers of groups A and E had the lowest flexural strength and modulus values, measuring at 87MPa and 3.43GPa, respectively. These findings have to do with the matrices' chemical make-up, the copolymer chains' chemical structures, and the types of chemical bonds joining the monomers together.

Figure (2): Flexural strength of the prepared copolymers (matrices) as a function of monomers groups (A, B, C, D, E and F).

Figure (3): Flexural modulus of the prepared copolymers (matrices) as a function of monomers groups (A, B, C, D, E and F).

Based on the results obtained from Figures 2 and 3, two samples of matrix materials were selected, one with the highest values in bending properties and the other having the lowest values, these samples represented by two groups of matrix monomers D and E, respectively. These materials were reinforced with hydroxyapatite nanoparticles, to prepare nanocomposites for dental materials.

Effect of nano fillers content:

The effect of adding different amounts of nano-hydroxyapatite (0, 1, 2, 3, and 4) wt.% with a constant amount of zinc oxide (0.4gm) as antimicrobial agent on the flexural strength and flexural modulus of the dental restorative hybrid nanocomposites materials, was shown in Figures (4) and (5), respectively.

There is a primary increase in the flexural strength and flexural modulus of the hybrid nanocomposites when adding 1% ratio of nano-powder hydroxyapatite were the values of flexural strength and flexural modulus increased from 121 to 133MPa and from 4.04 to 4.67GPa respectively, for matrix of monomers group D and these properties increased from 87 to 103MPa and from 3.44 to 3.77GPa, respectively, for matrix of monomers group E.

The maximum values of flexural strength and flexural modulus have been observed at ratio 2%wt of hydroxyapatite content, where it reached to 136MPa and 5.34GPa, respectively, for hybrid nanocomposites based on the matrix D, whereas, reached to 111MPa and 4GPa, respectively, for hybrid nanocomposites based on the matrix E.

Figure (4): Flexural Strength for hybrid nanocomposites based on the matrix of groups D or E as a function of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles content in the composite.

Figure (5): Flexural modulus for hybrid nanocomposites based on the matrix of groups D or E as a function of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles content in the composite.

Other studied about the connecting between the properties of composites and the variation in filler ratios content, they found that the composites with high filler content show better mechanical and physical properties [12]. These studies look to be agreeing with the results of current study but to limited content, it was found the hybrid nanocomposite resins that contain on 2%wt of hydroxyapatite nanoparticle showed significantly the higher values of flexural strength and flexural modulus as mentioned earlier, after this ratio of hydroxyapatite nanoparticle specifically at ratios (3 and 4) %wt., these properties decreased in their values.

A similar result was also showed by many researches that found the extra increasing in the used filler amount may be leads to a decrease in flexural strength [13]. These results indicated that the successful function of reinforcement by nanoparticle would not be accomplished at high ratios of

weight fraction, perhaps these large amounts can effect in formation of fillers agglomerates, which considered as weak points in composites (structural defects); next the existence of such agglomerates would decrease the mechanical properties (particularly strength property) of dental composites that reinforced by nanoparticles. [14, 15]

Other reason explained this behavior such as decrease the effective load-bearing cross-section of the resin matrix at concentration of nano-filler higher than limited content [16]; as well as, high ratios of filler content in composite usually caused a poor adhesion between filler and matrix.

Moreover, it was noticed from figures 4 and 5 that the rate of increased in flexural strength and flexural modulus depends on matrix monomers content of groups D and E.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the content of fillers does not individually affect the mechanical properties, but other factors such as size and type of filler, matrix composition, amount of initiators and microstructure morphology contribute to the improvement of physical and mechanical properties. [17].

Types of nano-filler: Based on forgoing results, it was choosing the best percentage (2%wt) nano-fillers content. Then added different types of nano-fillers (ZrO_2 , SiO_2 , HA and Al_2O_3) individually to each group of matrixes monomers (A, B, C, D, E and F) that mentioned earlier in Table 1 and at constant ratio of weight fraction (2%wt). Figures (6) and (7) show the flexural strength and flexural modulus of hybrid nanocomposites materials for dental restorative as a function of matrix type.

These figures showed a remarkable increase in flexural strength and flexural modulus with adding (2 %wt.) ratio of nanoparticles (ZrO_2 , SiO_2 , HA, and Al_2O_3) individually in the matrix monomers of the groups (A, B, C, D, E and F), as compared with the analogues of the matrices from which it is built. The rate of increment in flexural strength and flexural modulus values are dependent on the fillers type, as well as, on the matrix type (copolymers materials), and their properties [18, 19].

As well as, it can be seen that, the flexural strength and flexural modulus values are varying within the individual group; this is related to use the different types of nanoparticles from ceramic fillers.

Furthermore, it was established from these Figures that, the average values of flexural strength for all the prepared nanocomposite specimens range from the lowest value (87 MPa) for composite that based on matrix group (E) and reinforced with ZrO_2 nanoparticles to the highest value (144MPa) for composite that based on matrix group (D) and reinforced with SiO_2 nanoparticles.

Furthermore, was noticed that the matrix monomers of group D that reinforced by SiO_2 nanoparticles showed the highest value of elastic modulus (5.47GPa) in compare with all other composites, while the lowest values (3.43GPa) were recorded with the matrix monomers group (A) that reinforced by ZrO_2 nanoparticles.

And upon it, all the prepared hybrid nanocomposites materials of dental restorative achieve higher the flexural strength values than ones that proposed by the ISO suggesting, so all these composites can further used as direct restoration for the damaged dental materials.

On other hand, the results showed that the maximum value of flexural strength was obtained for all the prepared copolymers composites when reinforced there with silica nanoparticles followed by these reinforced by hydroxyapatite, alumina, zirconia nanoparticles which were added to all the prepared matrices. This related to the small size of silica and hydroxyapatite fillers particle which are (10-20 nm) and 25nm, respectively, contributes to increased mechanical strength due to increased

contact surface area of these particles with organic resin [15].

Figure (6): Flexural strength of prepared hybrid nanocomposites as a function of fillers type and the type of matrix material (monomers group of copolymers materials).

Figure (7): Flexural modulus of prepared hybrid nanocomposites as a function of fillers type and

the type of matrix material (monomers group of copolymers materials).

These findings support the notion that the manufactured dental composites, which are based on several novel kinds of matrix material monomers and include nanoparticles, have better flexural capabilities.

These findings corroborate earlier findings that the characteristics of monomers, such as their chemical make-up and chain structure, have a significant impact on how composites behave. As a result, more flexible composite resin is produced, and this flexibility increases the resin's flexural strength and flexural modulus while lowering brittleness. [20, 21]

The mechanical characteristics of composites are directly influenced by the chemical makeup of the monomers present in the resin. Prior studies have shown that flexural strength increases when TEGDMA is partially replaced with 1-6 HDDA (Note Table No. 1). Additionally, because of Image processing's greater viscosity than other monomers, a reduction in flexural strength was seen when it was combined with other monomers [22]. This is a unique explanation that might help to understand the findings of the present investigation.

The highest values of flexural strength and flexural modulus have been gained by nanocomposites that are based on the monomers matrix that contain on meth acrylamide of (group D) and are (144 MPa) and (5.47 GPa), respectively. This was much higher than the other tested materials, flowed by, and may be explain the reason for the higher flexural properties with the same type of nano-filler material.

The inclusion of nanoparticle filler is the second component that affected the characteristics of the composite. Figures 6 and 7 show that the inclusion of nanopowders typically improved the flexural characteristics of copolymer-composites; the pace of improvement is influenced by the kind of reinforcement used and by how well the reinforcement adheres to the matrix.

The capacity of nanoparticle fillers to create composite materials with strong physical bonds is one of the causes; as a consequence, a larger flexural stress is needed to cause breakage, increasing the flexural modulus and strength. Additionally, the rise is the result of certain nano-powders' capacity to boost resistance to crack formation. These nano-powders also have a tendency to hinder the development of microcracks, which are known to further reduce the mechanical characteristics of composite resins[23].

In addition, the uniform dispersion of nano-fillers in the composite materials and the strong interfacial interface between the organic matrix and inorganic fillers produce a homogeneous distribution of stresses, which prevents stress concentration and results in a significant improvement in the mechanical properties of the resulting composites. The good interfacial adhesion between the resin and fillers, together with the homogenous dispersion, improve the mechanical characteristics of composites [23, 24].

In actuality, the primary determinant of this variation in outcomes is connected to the characteristics and structure of each kind of filler, as well as their capacity to promote crystal deposition and growth on designed teeth.

A crucial aspect that must be taken into account when reinforcing resin to create dental composites

is the strong link that exists between resin and fillers in these materials. As a result, the excellent connectivity between fillers and resin might be linked to the high flexural strength shown in this research.

Although the relationship between the filler type and the variation in flexural properties is intriguing, the primary causes of this result are likely quite complicated and involved a number of factors related to particle size and geometry, filler morphology, and homogeneity of fillers distribution in matrix [25].

Conclusion: From this study, can be concluded the following:

1. Through image processing, brand-new dental restorative nanocomposites with distinctive monomers and various fillers were effectively created.
2. It is also proven that the examined innovative dental composites' flexural characteristics fall within the permissible range for dental ISO criteria.
3. By adding nanofillers to polymer resin in accordance with their kind and the chemical makeup of the matrix monomers materials, the flexural strength and modulus were enhanced.
4. The various components of the produced nanocomposite displayed diverse flexural characteristics that were related to their chemical make-up and the interaction between the organic and inorganic phases at their interfaces.
5. The presence of silica nanoparticles, methacrylamide, and methacrylic acid monomers in the dental restorative nanocomposite is the reason for the greater values of flexural characteristics that were obtained in this research.
6. One of the most promising samples for dental restoration and repair is a dental restorative nanocomposite made from group D matrix monomers and reinforced with 2% silica nanoparticles.

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